

EVALUATION OF DAMAGE MECHANISM OF $\pm 45^\circ$ FLAT BRAIDED CFRP COMPOSITES CONTAINING CARBON NANOFIBERS UNDER TENSILE LOADING WITH ASSISTANCE OF SQUID TECHNIQUE

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1 Abstract

The aim of this study is to provide an adequate understanding for the damage mechanism of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing Vapor Grown Carbon Nano-Fibers (VGCF) under off-axis tensile loading based on in-situ macroscopic surface observations of the in-plane cracking behavior and off-line measurements via Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) technique of the state-of-fibers. These three phase composites are successfully produced by modifying the hand lay-up technique by pre-impregnation of flat braided fabrics with mixture of resin and VGCF in vacuum. Stress-strain responses and fracture behavior were conjugated to quantify the effect of VGCF on the mechanical performance of the braided composites. The edges of these composites were cut to analyze the effect of the continuously oriented carbon fibers of all braided bundles on the tensile and in-plane shear properties. This study showed that SQUID technique is an effective tool for inspecting the state-of-failure of carbon fiber bundles, whereas the in-situ surface macroscopic observation technique is a useful technique for observing the surface matrix cracking at different stages of fracture. The damage mechanism of uncut-edges and cut-edges of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing VGCF are adequately identified.

2 Introduction

In the braided fabric, all fiber bundles are continuously oriented therefore the composites have

superior mechanical properties. One of the features of the braided fabrics is the capability of changing the braiding angle. Another feature is the capability of inserting bundles called the middle-end-fiber (MEF) bundles into the braiding fibers along the longitudinal direction. In addition, various kinds of braiding fiber bundles and MEF bundles with different properties can be used in hybrid braided composites to meet the requirements of composite structures. Therefore the mechanical properties of braided composite can be changed by selecting the type and number of fiber bundles for both of the braiding fiber and MEF bundles as well as by changing the braiding angle.

Although several studies [1-5] have been carried out to investigate the mechanical properties of braided composites, only few studies have been conducted to clarify the conjugation of mechanical properties and fracture behavior of Braided CFRP composites. Amongst these few studies, Aly-Hassan et al. has investigated recently the damage mechanism of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites with assistance of in-situ macroscopic surface observations of the in-plane cracking behavior and off-line measurements via Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) technique of the state-of-fibers. The damage mechanism of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites was sufficiently recognized and these composites have exhibited a slight fiber scissoring mechanism at final fracture stage, i.e. re-orientation of braiding fiber bundles with smaller angle than the original $\pm 45^\circ$ braiding angle of the fabricated composites, followed by a partially fiber failure [6]. The tensile and shear strengths of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided

CFRP composites were enhanced by dispersing carbon nanotubes/nanofibers uniformly into the epoxy matrix of these composites as reported in Ref. [7]. Therefore, a sufficient understand for the damage mechanism of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing Vapor Grown Carbon Nano-Fibers (VGCF) under tensile loading is essentially required to attain high reliability for using these three phase flat braided CFRP composites as primary load bearing structures. This is what has been done in this research.

3 Experimental Procedures

3.1 Composite System

First, flat carbon fabrics with braiding angle of $\pm 45^\circ$ were braided via automated braider using 24 carbon yarns of PAN-based carbon fibers ($\phi = 7 \mu\text{m}$, HTA-12K, Toho Tenax). The carbon nanofibers used in this study were vapor grown carbon nanofibers, or so called VGCFTM, that were obtained from Showa Denko KK, Japan with diameters of 100~150 nm and lengths of 10~20 μm . Next, in order to disperse VGCFs into the epoxy matrix, three-step mixing procedures were employed. Drying the VGCFs was carried out by heating to 110 °C in a vacuum for 5 h in order to remove the moisture. Then, 2wt% of VGCFs were combined with the epoxy using sonication and mechanical stirring simultaneously at 70 °C for 15 min and finally the blended VGCF-dispersed epoxy was vacuumed at 70 °C for another 15 min to remove the voids. After that, the $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided carbon fabrics were dipped in bath full by the above-mentioned VGCF-dispersed epoxy in vacuum condition at 70 °C for 10 min. This vacuum condition helps to remove the entrapped air between fibers and high temperature condition decreases the viscosity of the VGCF-dispersed epoxy to be able to flow it through the fabric and gels maturely in addition to achieve uniform dispersion of non-aggregated VGCF in the epoxy resin as much as possible during the impregnation process. Finally, the hand lay-up technique was employed to fabricate coupon composites with $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided carbon reinforcements with loading percentage of VGCF about 2 wt%, in the epoxy matrix. The curing condition of the composite of 80 °C for 3 hours and post curing condition of 120 °C for 6 hours were

carried out to obtain finally the composites with micro-fiber volume fraction about 50 %.

3.2 Tensile Testing

Uniaxial tension tests for the composites were performed for evaluation of in-plane shear and tensile responses using expressions derived from the laminated plate theory. The in-plane shear stresses, in-plane shear strains and initial in-plane shear moduli were calculated by the following equations.

$$\tau_{12}^i = P_x^i / 2bd \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{12}^i = \varepsilon_x^i - \varepsilon_y^i \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = \Delta \tau_{12} / \Delta \gamma_{12} \quad (3)$$

where τ , γ , G , ε_x , ε_y , b and d are the in-plane shear stress, shear strain in-plane, in-plane shear modulus, longitudinal normal strain, lateral normal strain, specimen width and specimen thickness, respectively. The geometrical shape and dimensions of tensile specimens of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing dispersed VGCF through its epoxy matrix, uncut-edges specimens and cut-edges specimens, respectively are illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Tensile specimens

3.3 In-Situ Macroscopic Observation

In-situ macroscopic observations using high-resolution digital video camera for the fracture behavior on the specimen surfaces under tensile loading were carried out to help to identify the real

damage mechanism and to understand the effect of the continuously oriented fibers at the edges. The surfaces of the tensile specimen types were softly painted by a thin layer of a water-based white color to enable us to observe the initiation, propagations and pattern system of the surface cracks. This is can be accomplished straightforwardly from the contrast between the black color of the composites and the white color of the surface painting. This simple technique has been used effectively in observing the matrix cracking and splitting for 2D C/C composites [8-11].

3.3 SQUID Measurements

Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID) technique was employed as off-line non-destructive inspection (NDI) for the resulting damage in the composites due to the tensile mechanical loadings. The purpose of using SQUID technique is mainly to evaluate the state-of-fibers at early stage of mechanical loadings that is not detectable in either of the load-displacement curve or through the in-situ macroscopic observation of damage on the specimen surface. Such kind of additional measurements of the real damage mechanism is essentially required for investigating the mechanical and fracture behavior of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing Vapor Grown Carbon Nano-Fibers (VGCF) to identify to a deeper and clear knowledge of the effect of the continuously oriented carbon fibers at the composite edges but also to clarify and evaluate the failure mechanism of the flat braided composites. This useful technique has been used efficiently in observing the state-of-fibers for 2D and 3D C/C composites after compact tests [12-14].

In this study, a high critical temperature Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (High Tc-SQUID) gradiometer system in an electromagnetically well shielded environment was used to inspect the state-of-fibers in the composites at various stages of tensile loadings. This system was composed of a High Tc-SQUID gradiometer which was cooled at 77 K with a pulse tube cryocooler, a differential rectangular pickup coils, SQUID electronics, an XY scanning stage system, a lock-in amplifier, head amplifier, functional generator, thermostat, and PC, as illustrated in Figure 2. More details about this SQUID are published elsewhere [15].

A low-frequency sinusoidal current of 9 mA and 800 Hz was injected directly through the in-plane direction of the tensile specimens of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites. Then, the gradients of magnetic flux density (magnetic field) in x-direction (dBz/dy) and in y-direction (dBz/dx) were measured under a lift-off distance of 2 or 3 mm for as-fabricated and as-fractured specimens, respectively and under a sampling space of 1 mm in the x- and y-directions. The magnetic flux background noise at 800 Hz was $17 \mu\Phi_0/\text{Hz}^{1/2}$. To eliminate the background noise, an unflawed copper sheet was placed beneath the flat braided CFRP samples. Since low-frequency current was used in this study, the time-dependent term in Maxwell equation could be neglected. In addition, the gradient of magnetic flux density (B) with respect to the z (thickness)-direction was substantially smaller than those with respect to other X and Y directions, due to the use of thin specimens. Thus, the Maxwell equation was reduced as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\mu} \left(\frac{\partial B_z}{\partial y} \right) \approx J_x \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu} \left(\frac{\partial B_z}{\partial x} \right) \approx J_y \quad (5)$$

where J and μ are the current density and magnetic permeability, respectively, and subscripts x and y represent the vector components. In the present experiments, a uniform electric current was injected into of uncut-edges and cut-edges specimens for both of as-fabricated and as-fractured $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composite materials containing dispersed VGCF through the its epoxy matrix.

Fig. 2. High Tc-SQUID gradiometer system.

Measurements of magnetic field gradients (dBz/dy , dBz/dx) will be repeated to detect the different stages of damage; specifically for undamaged stage, partially damaged stage and final damaged stage of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites under tensile loadings for both of uncut-edges and cut-edges specimens. Since the current densities (J_x , J_y) flowing in the samples are roughly proportional to the generated magnetic field gradients (dBz/dy , dBz/dx) as proved in Equations 4 and 5, current maps furthermore can be obtained to illustrate the current disturbance due to the existed damage on the current flow through the in-plane direction of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites. Using the above-mentioned procedure, the surface or subsurface fiber failure or fiber irregularities could be identified either qualitatively or quantitatively.

4 Results and Discussions

Summary of the in-plane shear and tensile properties which obtained from the tensile tests of $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens for both of flat braided CFRP composites containing dispersed VGCF through the its epoxy matrix with edges and without edges is listed in Table 1.

Properties Specimen Type	Shear Strength (MPa)	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
Uncut-Edges Specimens	175	6.19	350	26.5
Cut-Edges Specimens	139	5.15	278	22.1

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the composites.

Fig.3. Tensile stress-strain curve associated with the fracture behavior of cut-edges specimens

Compiling the fracture behavior that obtained from of the in-situ surface macroscopic technique, Figures 3 and 4, observing the surface cracking with the fracture behavior that obtained from SQUID measurements, examining the state-of-fibers failure, as shown in Figure 5, leded for identifying adequately the crucial effect of the VGCF on the mechanical properties of $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites. The cut-edges composites have exhibited fiber failure whereas the uncut-edges composites have not exhibited fiber scissoring mechanism at final fracture stage in contrast with same composites without VGCF [6].

Fig. 4. Tensile stress-strain curve associated with the fracture behavior of uncut-edges specimens.

Fig.5. Magnetic field gradients (dBz/dy) in x-direction obtained by SQUID sensor (a) Cut-edges specimen. (b) Uncut-edges

5 Conclusion

The enhancement of the tensile and in-plane strengths of the uncut-edges $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites by about 60% higher than those of the cut-edges $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites containing dispersed VGCF through the its epoxy matrix has not achieved by the effect of re-orientation of braiding fiber bundles with smaller

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angle than the original $\pm 45^\circ$ braiding angle of the fabricated composites, or so called fiber scissoring mechanism in composites, that observed in uncut-edges $\pm 45^\circ$ of flat braided CFRP composites without VGCF [6] but only by the effect of the continuously oriented carbon fibers at the edges. Off-line measurements by SQUID technique is very effective non-destructive method to inspect the state-of-fiber failure for the $\pm 45^\circ$ flat braided CFRP composites with VGCF and without VGCF [6], while the in-situ surface macroscopic technique is useful on observing the surface matrix cracking. Therefore, the integration of both techniques is very helpful to analyze the reasons of failure by understanding the relationships among the real fracture behavior, damage mechanism and mechanical properties for CFRP composites. The SQUID technique could be a prospective candidate for confirmation of structural integrity of the braided structures, for monitoring of carbon braiding process and as proof test for braiding machines.

Nomenclature

CFRP	Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer
VGCF	Vapor Grown Carbon Nano-Fibers
MEF	Middle-End-Fiber
SQUID	Superconducting Quantum Interference Device
PAN	Polyacrylonitrile
C/C	Carbon/Carbon Composites
ASTM	American Society of Testing and Materials
NDI	Non-Destructive Inspection
T _c	Critical temperature
b	Width of the specimen (mm)
d	Thickness of the specimen (mm)
ϵ_x	Longitudinal normal strain (-)
ϵ_y	Lateral normal strain (-)
γ	In-plane shear strain (-)
G	In-plane shear modulus (GPa)
τ	In-plane shear stress (MPa)
2D	Two dimensional
3D	Three dimensional
J	Current density
J _x	Current density in X-direction
J _y	Current density in Y-direction
μ	Magnetic permeability
dBz/dy	Gradients of magnetic flux density

(magnetic field) in X-direction
dBz/dx Gradients of magnetic flux density
(magnetic field) in Y-direction

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